

A Method for Detection and Evaluation of Driver Distraction Induced by In-Vehicle Information Systems

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Abstract—Steep improvement of an in-vehicle info- and entertainment systems has a positive impact on vehicle control, comfort, safety, etc. Nevertheless, it also leads to a multitasking load increase on the in-vehicle information system due to fundamental problems of driver distraction. In this paper, a method for detection and evaluation of driver distraction induced by the driver’s secondary activity is developed. The methodology is based on the machine learning and computation intelligence algorithms blend, which includes a driver model, a driver distraction detector, and a fuzzy logic evaluator. Several data fitting algorithms efficient for nonlinear regression are designed and are compared on the accuracy of the driver performance prediction. The method is verified by the driver-in-the-loop experiment with thirty participants on an advanced vehicle simulator. Driver’s interaction with the commercial in-vehicle information system is exploited as a secondary distractive task.

Keywords—Prediction methods; regression analysis; fuzzy logic; computational intelligence; vehicle safety; man-machine systems

I. INTRODUCTION

With a rapid development of the in-vehicle information systems (IVIS), driver distraction (DD) becomes a new serious challenge for on-ground vehicle safety. DD is defined as “anything that delays the recognition of information necessary to safety maintain the lateral and longitudinal control of the vehicle (driver’s primary task) due to some event, activity, object or person (driver’s secondary activity), within or outside the vehicle that compels or tends to induce the driver’s shifting attention away from the fundamental driving task by compromising the driver’s auditory, biomechanical, cognitive or visual faculties or combinations thereof.” Almost 3500 people are killed and almost 400000 people are injured in the traffic accidents by distracted driving annually in the USA alone. In the EU, 20% of all fatalities on the road are due to DD. Unfortunately, this trend does not tend to decline [1], [2].

To improve vehicle safety, IVIS-induced DD detection and following minimization via human-machine interface (HMI)

design are the essential tasks for all vehicle manufacturers. The objective of this study is the development of a robust DD detection and evaluation methodology, which is capable not only to detect DD, but also to measure precisely its impact on safe vehicle operation for further DD minimization via vehicle cockpit design.

Some DD evaluation methods are based on subjective evaluation (e.g. questionnaire, survey) [3], [4], which depends on expert’s judgment and cannot be accepted as a fair evaluation. Therefore, scholars proposed different solutions for DD detection using modern practical machine learning and soft computing algorithms relying on behavioral (e.g. eye and head movement) attributes. For instance, in [5], k -nearest neighbor (k -NN), graph-regularized extreme learning machine and support vector machine (SVM) were compared on DD detection accuracy. Fuzzy logic (FL) [6], and artificial neural network (ANN) combined with gradient boosting machine [7] were also considered. Other researchers trusted the psychological attributes (e.g. electrocardio- and electroencephalographical signals). In [8], decision tree, random forest, k -NN, SVM, and Naïve Bayes algorithms were compared, while in [9] the Bayesian network and logic regression were used. The reliance on additional devices, such as cameras and neuroscan system, is the methods’ main drawback, because it rises the system price and complexity [10]. Moreover, this equipment is often considered as distractive.

Consequently, the performance-based attributes (e.g. vehicle lateral and longitudinal dynamics) are more feasible for practical application, because, in this case, DD detection and evaluation mechanism is supported by the signals transmitted from the sensors available in modern vehicles (e.g. vehicle speed, steering wheel rotation, vehicle acceleration, etc.). In [11], Gaussian mixture model was designed for DD detection. In [12], [13], the same algorithm was combined with ANN. Other computational intelligence and statistical learning theory approaches, like SVM [14], fuzzy logic [15], ANN with SVM [16], [17] were also applied for induced by secondary activity DD classification.

Although the accuracy of the proposed methods for DD detection is very high, all previously suggested approaches represent the binary logic classifiers, i.e. distracted/non-distracted. Thus, the methods are not applicable for precise measurement and evaluation of the secondary activity effect on the vehicle safe operation. Consequently, a new method for detecting and accurate measuring the secondary task impact on the DD level was developed by the authors [18].

In this paper, however, the method is enhanced with additional driver performance variable, namely steering wheel acceleration, and with one additional characteristic of the road segment. These innovations lead to the FL evaluator re-design that accordingly, provides more accurate DD evaluation. Hence, three performance-based variables are blended for DD detection and evaluation, instead of two in [18].

Furthermore, as the machine learning theory contains a vast variety of prediction algorithms [19], [20], different techniques for solving nonlinear regression problems, such as Gaussian process regression model (GPRM), ANN, layer-recurrent neural network (LRNN), adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS), and k -NN are applied for driver modelling. The prediction models are compared in this study to determine the most accurate one. In [18], though, only the most commonly used prediction model ANN was applied. This paper tends to find the most accurate prediction model among the studied ones here. The algorithms are verified by the driver-in-the-loop experiment on an advanced driver decoy simulator, where DD is caused by various tasks from IVIS.

This paper is organized as follows. The DD detection and evaluation mechanism is described in the next section. In Section III, data collection is explained. Thereafter, the results of the drive-in-the-loop experiment are introduced. Finally, the studies are concluded in Section V.

II. DRIVER DISTRACTION DETECTION AND EVALUATION METHOD

The block scheme of the DD detection and evaluation method is introduced in Fig. 1. The parameters description is presented in Table I. The method involves three steps.

First, the Driver model (Predictor) block predicts driver's performance on a road segment, which is described by three properties: speed limit v_l , road curvature c_r , and road curve direction c_d . The last feature may have three variables: -1 – the road leads to the left; 1 – to the right; or 0, when the road is

Fig. 1. Driver distraction detection and evaluation method block scheme.

straight. The predictor uses preliminary collected data and applies a machine learning algorithm for vehicle dynamic performance prediction (i.e. vehicle speed deviation Δv_p , lane keeping ability Δx_p , and steering wheel acceleration a_p). The Driver model is unique for every person.

Next, the predicted vehicle longitudinal and lateral dynamics are compared with the same performance variables collected while driving under DD: Δv , Δx , and a . In this phase the resultative performance, which is described by three parameters (i.e. Δv_r , Δx_r , a_r) is calculated. The following rules are applied to each parameter (the example is shown only for Δv_r calculation):

$$\Delta v_r = \begin{cases} \Delta v - \Delta v_p, & \text{if } \Delta v > 0; \Delta v_p > 0; |\Delta v| > |\Delta v_p| \\ \Delta v - \Delta v_p, & \text{if } \Delta v < 0; \Delta v_p < 0; |\Delta v| > |\Delta v_p| \\ \Delta v + \Delta v_p, & \text{if } \Delta v > 0; \Delta v_p < 0; |\Delta v| > |\Delta v_p| \\ \Delta v + \Delta v_p, & \text{if } \Delta v < 0; \Delta v_p > 0; |\Delta v| > |\Delta v_p| \\ 0, & \text{if } |\Delta v| \leq |\Delta v_p| \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

In short, the block outputs zero, when the performance value under DD is smaller than the predicted one. If the DD performance value is greater than predicted value, the difference between two variables is calculated. Therefore, the difference symbolizes, how much does the secondary activity influence the vehicle dynamic performance from the safety point of view? Negative resultative performance, Δv_r , Δx_r , and a_r , means driving slower its speed limit, driving on a right side from the road middle line, and turning a steering wheel to the right, correspondingly. Contrariwise, positive resultative values represent speeding, driving to the left from the center of the lane, and steering to the left, accordingly.

Finally, the resultative performance enters the Evaluator block. In this stage, the intelligent FL algorithm fuses three variables into a single output. The output represents DD in percentage and is utilized as a DD evaluation coefficient.

A. Driver Model

Various practically used machine learning algorithms may be exploited in the Predictor model. In this paper, the prediction results of the most superb ones for solving nonlinear regression matter, namely GPRM, ANN, LRNN, ANFIS, and k -NN, are developed and are compared between each other.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS DESCRIPTION

Symbol	Description	Unit
v_l	Speed limit	km/h
c_r	Road curve radius	m
c_d	Road curve direction	Left/Right
Δx	Real lane keeping offset	m
Δv	Real vehicle speed deviation	km/h
a	Real steering wheel acceleration	$^\circ/s^2$
Δx_p	Predicted lane keeping offset	m
Δv_p	Predicted vehicle speed deviation	km/h
a_p	Predicted steering wheel acceleration	$^\circ/s^2$
Δx_r	Resultative lane keeping offset	m
Δv_r	Resultative vehicle speed deviation	km/h
a_r	Resultative steering wheel acceleration	$^\circ/s^2$
DD	Driver distraction level	%

Due to the software simplicity, all the algorithms were designed with MATLAB R2016b from MathWorks, Inc (Natick, Massachusetts, United States). In this sub-section, these algorithms are briefly described.

1) *Gaussian Process Regression Model*: Gaussian process methods are widely used for regression problem, where the predicted values are continuous quantities. The GPRM are nonparametric kernel-based probabilistic models with the main advantage of simplicity of implementation and interpretability. However, the algorithm has also a significant disadvantage, because its prediction accuracy degrades if the mapping between inputs and outputs cannot be approximated by a linear function. For more details about GPRM, the readers may refer to the Chapter 2 in [21]. In this work, the GPRM is trained using the linear basis function and exact prediction method.

2) *Artificial Neural Network*: ANN is the feedforward multilayer perceptron, while the multilayer perceptron is a mathematical function mapping the input-output values. The ANN contains an input layer, at least one hidden layer of computational neurons, and an output layer [20], [22]. In this work, the ANN with two hidden layers and 100 neurons in each hidden layer is trained with the Levenberg-Marquardt learning algorithm. The method is fast and efficient for the nonlinear regression problem. In this method, the gradients are computed by a backward propagation of errors, what makes it the most rapid and efficient algorithm. Thanks to their simplicity, the sigmoid activation functions were used in hidden layer neurons, while the output neuron transfer functions are linear. Number of neurons in the hidden layers is responsible for model exactness. At the same time, more neurons in the layers lead to network's computational cost growth [22]. In the designed ANN, an improvement of the network performance has not been noticed with more than 100 neurons. Initially the hyperparameters are set by default in the software, however, the training parameters, namely initial weights and threshold levels, are selected randomly.

3) *Layer-Recurrent Neural Network*: The difference between LRNN and ANN is that the first one has a feedback loops (with a delay) from its output to its next input. The network uses the hyperbolic tangent sigmoid transfer functions for the hidden layers and the linear transfer function in the output layer. More information about the recurrent and recursive nets can be found in Chapter 10 in [20]. In this work, the LRNN, as ANN, was trained with the Levenberg-Marquardt method. The network contains 15 neurons in the hidden layer. The input delay of the feedback signal from the hidden layer is 1:2.

4) *Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System*: ANFIS is an equivalent to a first-order Sugeno's fuzzy model. The model is a combination of the two most popular computational intelligence algorithms: ANN and FL. The network is a six-layer feedforward ANN that uses a hybrid training method, which combines the back-propagation algorithm in the backward pass and least squares - in the forward pass, to

optimize both the antecedent and the consequent parameters [21], [23]. The greater number of membership functions (MFs), rather than their shape, improves the model efficiency. This is because the number of MFs directly influences the amount of linguistic links between inputs and outputs allowing more precise ANFIS tuning [21]. In this work, the ANFIS contains nine MFs for each input variable. They are symmetrically dispersed and overlapped between each other over the whole universe of discourse (UOD). The MFs have triangular shapes, because they are simple for programming. The output MFs are linear.

5) *k-Nearest Neighbor*: k -NN represents the last algorithm used as the Predictor. The algorithm for storing the input-output training set is enough simple. When requested, it searches the closest entry in the data set and returns the associated target. The main advantage of the algorithm is its ability to achieve the minimum possible training error on any regression data kit. Thus, it makes the algorithm one of the most accurate for prediction from a simple data sample. Nevertheless, at the same time it makes the method computationally expensive for real-time applications [19], [20]. In our case, $k = 1$. Hence, a new input (v_i, c_r, c_d) representing the sample data from driving under DD, searches a nearest point from the preliminary gathered data (v_i^t, c_r^t, c_d^t). As a result, the predicted performance is returned ($\Delta y_p, \Delta x_p, a_p$), which corresponds to an appropriate point from the training data set ($\Delta y^t, \Delta x^t, a^t$).

B. Fuzzy Logic Evaluator

The FL evaluator has three inputs (i.e. $\Delta y_r, \Delta x_r, a_r$) and a single output, DD. In this work, a Sugeno's type inference mechanism based on simple matrix operation is applied [24], where the inputs are fuzzified into a $5 \times 5 \times 3$ matrix. Due to its

TABLE II. FUZZY LOGIC EVALUATOR RULE-BASE

$a_r = \text{negative}$						
DD [%]		Δx_r				
		<i>neg_far</i>	<i>neg_close</i>	<i>zero</i>	<i>pos_close</i>	<i>pos_far</i>
Δv_r	<i>neg_high</i>	100	85.8	42.9	85.8	100
	<i>neg_low</i>	100	57.2	14.3	57.2	100
	<i>zero</i>	57.2	28.6	0	28.6	57.2
	<i>pos_low</i>	85.8	42.9	14.3	42.9	85.8
	<i>pos_high</i>	100	85.8	42.9	85.8	100
$a_r = \text{zero}$						
DD [%]		Δx_r				
		<i>neg_far</i>	<i>neg_close</i>	<i>zero</i>	<i>pos_close</i>	<i>pos_far</i>
Δv_r	<i>neg_high</i>	100	71.5	42.9	71.5	100
	<i>neg_low</i>	85.8	14.3	0	14.3	85.8
	<i>zero</i>	42.9	0	0	0	42.9
	<i>pos_low</i>	71.5	14.3	0	14.3	71.5
	<i>pos_high</i>	85.8	57.2	28.6	57.2	85.5
$a_r = \text{positive}$						
DD [%]		Δx_r				
		<i>neg_far</i>	<i>neg_close</i>	<i>zero</i>	<i>pos_close</i>	<i>pos_far</i>
Δv_r	<i>neg_high</i>	100	85.8	42.9	85.8	100
	<i>neg_low</i>	100	57.2	14.3	57.2	100
	<i>zero</i>	57.2	28.6	0	28.6	57.2
	<i>pos_low</i>	85.8	42.9	14.3	42.9	85.8
	<i>pos_high</i>	100	85.8	42.9	85.8	100

simplicity, all the input MFs have triangular shapes, where both Δv_r and Δx_r have five MFs and a_r – three MFs. The MFs are symmetrically dispersed and overlapped between each other over the whole UOD, what gives them equal sensitivity. The Δy_r is bounded in $[-12, 12]$, the Δx_r OUD is closed in $[-1.5, 1.5]$, and a_r - inside $[-1500, 1500]$.

The input and output mapping is done via 75 linguistic rules. The rule-base is lodged in Table II. As the fuzzified from the input matrix size is $5 \times 5 \times 3$, the rule-base has three different tables for each layer of the three-dimensional matrix. The UOD of the output is restricted in $[0, 100]$, because the final output represents the level of DD in percentage. Eight linear-form MFs are designed for the output. The output MFs are dissipated on equal step 14.3 between each other. An example of the modus-ponens-form rules connection is as follows: **IF** the steering wheel acceleration is “*positive*”, **AND** vehicle speed deviation is “*pos_low*”, **AND** lane keeping offset is “*pos_far*”, **THEN** driver distraction is 85.8 %.

III. DATA COLLECTION

A. Participants

Thirty drivers without serious physical or mental health disorders, who use passenger vehicles daily contributed to the driver-in-the-loop experiment. Participants’ female – male ratio was 5 to 25. The contributors’ gender, age, and driving experience and statistical analysis on DD level were not under the scope of the studies. The participation was not voluntarily, but rewarded.

B. Apparatus

The real-time driver-in-the-loop experiment was conducted using the advanced driver decoy simulator provided by the ŠKODA Auto a.s. HMI laboratory (Mladá Boleslav, Czech Republic). The simulator is a fixed-base test rig with an identical to a commercial vehicle cockpit. The driver operates the simulator in the virtual world, which is displayed on the wall in front of the test bed. All the secondary activities are submitted via cockpit HMI. The data are collected with 10 Hz frequency. More information about the experiment facilities, including the simulator, software, vehicle modelling and parameterization, can be found in [18].

C. Procedure

The driver-in-the-loop experiment consisted of two phases. In the first phase, each driver was requested to drive the simulator in the virtual world staying in the middle of the road

Fig. 2. Driver-in-the-loop experiment procedure.

and holding the speed limit, as she/he would do in the real world. The data collected during this step were expended for the Predictor design. The two-lane road is identical to one of the road segments in Czech Republic, where each lane is 3.5 m width. The road shape has two main segments: 50 km/h speed limit with curvy shape, and almost straight road with 90 km/h speed limitation. There were no other dynamic objects (e.g. other vehicles, people or animals) modelled in the virtual world.

During the second stage, the participants were requested to continue driving in the virtual world as accurate as possible. Simultaneously, this time they were obliged to accomplish the secondary tasks by interacting with IVIS. The drivers got different commands (such as searching for a specific radio station, selecting the new city in the navigation system, making a call to a specific contact, etc.) from the experimenter. After the secondary task submission, the participants had to give a feedback via a windshield washer switch behind the steering wheel. If the secondary task is completed wrong, the drivers were asked to repeat the activity.

In Fig. 2, the photo taken during the second stage is shown. One of the experiment contributors interacts with the IVIS while piloting the simulator in the virtual world. The data gathered during this phase were applied for DD detection and IVIS-induced DD evaluation.

Fig. 3. Prediction algorithms comparison for Δv_p versus training reference data.

Fig. 4. Prediction algorithms comparison for Δx_p versus training reference data.

Fig. 5. Prediction algorithms comparison for a_p versus training reference data.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, the results of the driver-in-the-loop experiment are introduced. A random driver is selected from the experiment participants. Her/his performance is studied here in details. For the rest of the experiment participants the outcomes are very similar. For better observation, only 10 minutes of the DD experiment are presented.

Vehicle speed deviation (Fig. 3), lane keeping ability (Fig. 4), steering wheel acceleration (Fig. 5) along with the curve representing the reference data (black line in each plot) are delivered. It is hard to distinguish the optimization curves for all studied nonlinear regression algorithms (i.e. k -NN, ANN, ANFIS, GPRM, and LRNN). Therefore, in Table III the models' performance accuracies are presented.

In Table III, the sum of the squared error of prediction (SSE), which is a main parameter for regression accuracy [21], is calculated for every variable and each Predictor. In addition, the model training time t_{train} as another important parameter of the real-time application is tracked for every variable. It is concluded that, for our task, the k -NN outperforms other multidimensional mapping algorithms in both SSE and training

TABLE III. THE PREDICTORS' PREDICTION ACCURACY COMPARISON

SSE	Δv_p	Δx_p	a_p	t_{train} [s]
GPRM	4.436	1.121	4.512	112.775
ANN	6.089	1.243	6.843	282.737
LRNN	1.243	1.340	6.890	231.515
ANFIS	6.843	1.216	6.678	155.720
k-NN	5.941	0.918	4.137	50.39

time features. This judgment also confirms the statement from [20] that the nearest neighbor regression, depending of the data sample, is one of the most accurate predictors.

In Fig. 6, DD evaluation results are scoped, where due to its excellent performance the k -NN is applied as the Driver model (Fig. 1). The gray background symbolizes the period of the secondary task accomplishment. Though there were different IVIS-induced distractive tasks requested from the participants, an investigation of each single task's impact on vehicle safety was not under the scope of this study. The white background indicates free from distraction driving. The red curve represents the level of DD inferred by the FL Evaluator.

In short, it can be noticed that some secondary activities led to a significantly high level of DD. Moreover, the drivers

Fig. 6. Driver distraction evaluation by fuzzy logic.

require more time to complete these tasks, what can be addressed to the tasks' complexity and consequent humans' cognitive workload increase. On the contrary, some tasks do not cause DD at all, what makes them safe for multitasking vehicle operation.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a new IVIS-induced DD detection and evaluation method is described. The methodology concerns the Driver model designed with help of machine learning algorithms, the comparative rules for DD detection, and the FL Evaluator algorithm. The last one melts three performance-based attributes (i.e. vehicle lane and speed limit keeping abilities, as well as applied on a steering wheel force) into a single output, which expresses a level of DD in percentage.

Various nonlinear regression techniques are used for the Predictor development. Based on prediction accuracy and algorithm training time, the k -NN outperformed other approaches, namely ANN, ANFIS, GPRM, and LRNN. The methodology is tested in driver-in-the-loop experiment with thirty participants. Overall, the method can be applied as a practical tool for evaluation of the driver's secondary activity influence on vehicle safe piloting.

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